

DETERMINATION OF THE LEVEL OF INFLUENCE OF GAMMA RADIATION ON THE ORGANISM (BASED ON AN EXPERIMENTAL MODEL)

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ABSTRACT

In order to adequately assess the effects of different doses of radiation (0.2 Gr and 5 Gr) on the body, experimental total acute and chronic radiation experimental models were created involving white rats.

As a result of numerous studies, it has been found that the effects of various external and internal factors on living organisms lead to various changes in the systems and organs of their organism, which are determined using medical and biological methods and the degree of changes is assessed. Based on this, it is noted that a pre-pathological or pathological state has occurred. External influences affecting the organism include acute and chronic radiation, which includes total irradiation of laboratory animals.

The purpose. Basics of creating experimental models for determining the level of influence of various forms of radiation on the body.

Material and methods. In order to adequately assess the effects of different doses of radiation (0.2 Gr and 5 Gr) on the body, experimental total acute and chronic radiation experimental models were created using non-white rats. Given that acute and chronic radiation exposure is most likely to occur in older people, laboratory animals were taken at the age of puberty (3 months), healthy, and weighing at least 160-180 g, and rats of this weight were selected for the study.

Results. In creating acute and chronic radiation models, laboratory animals were selected according to the following criteria: first, their structural and functional similarity to the human body, sensitivity to acute and chronic radiation; second, the cheapness and ease of finding this experimental material; third, the possibility of keeping it in vivarium conditions; fourth, the possibility of disposal after death. White outbred rats that met these criteria were selected to create an experimental model. In addition to these criteria, attention was paid to the age and weight of the white outbred rats to ensure the purity of experimental studies.

Since the laboratory animals were divided into 2 groups (group 1 - those who received the biologically active supplement (BA) "Lactonzopolis-AWL" for 30 days; group 2 - those who did not receive the BA "Lactonzopolis-AWL"), the results were presented by group. On the 1st day after acute irradiation, various changes in laboratory animals were observed in all of

them, and on the 4th day, a difference was observed in the numbers obtained between the groups. The results obtained showed that the total, single-time acute irradiation changed not only the organs and systems of the body, but also the response to external influences. It is noteworthy that with the passage of the 20-day chronic irradiation period, the changes in the condition of the experimental animals became more profound, but even then, at the end of the period, the indicators did not reach 100.0% and were in the range of 20.69-75.0%. Although the trend of changes in the condition and behavioral response of experimental animals that underwent preventive biocorrection with the onset of chronic radiation (group 1) was the same as that of those that did not undergo preventive biocorrection (group 2), the intensity of the changes differed significantly..

Conclusion. In order to adequately assess the effects of different doses of radiation (0.2 Gr and 5 Gr) on the body, experimental total acute and chronic radiation experimental models were created involving white rats.

